

Farmer Clusters: Working together to address the biodiversity crisis

Policy recommendations

To promote Farmer Clusters as an effective approach to improve biodiversity, environmental outcomes, and sustainability across farm landscapes the following policies are recommended:

- **Invest in long-term facilitation and support.** Government and rural development policies should embed training, resourcing, and financing for Farmer Cluster facilitators as core elements of agri-environmental programmes. By supporting skilled facilitators to build trust, coordinate activity, and link farmers to external expertise, policies can enable Farmer Clusters to deliver long-term benefits for biodiversity and rural communities.
- **Enhance access to advice, training, and monitoring tools.** Policy should prioritise funding for knowledge exchange platforms, tailored training, and shared monitoring protocols, ensuring farmers have the information, tools, and support needed to implement, assess, and adapt their conservation efforts within their clusters.
- **Maintain voluntary, group-based incentives within AES.** Maintain flexible incentives that reward collaborative action and enable collective results within AES. The unique Dutch approach to organise AES through regional ‘BoerenNatuur’ collectives is an example for other European countries on how to embed group result-based payments. Develop additional incentives for voluntary clustering of farms within these collectives as this reinforces both rural resilience and ecological benefits.

Transformative impact of Farmer Clusters on farmland biodiversity

Farmland biodiversity is in decline, threatening both agroecosystem services and long-term food system resilience. While agri-environmental schemes (AES) aim to reverse this trend, uptake and impact vary widely. Traditional top-down AES often fail to connect with farmers’ local realities, values, and identity. In contrast, the Farmer Cluster approach offers a promising alternative. Farmer Clusters empower farmers to achieve their farming and environmental goals. By working together under the guidance of a skilled facilitator, appointed by the collectives, farmers can tackle landscape-level restoration and have a greater impact than any one individual could accomplish alone. Using a “bottom-up” approach, farmers identify their conservation priorities and choose which practices to implement collectively. This is an impactful way to address global issues such as biodiversity conservation at the landscape scale. As well as the conservation benefits, Farmer Clusters can be focal points of the collectives and help to create support networks in rural communities, bridging gaps between policy-makers and farmers, and fostering both regional and national cohesion.

Approach and results

The **EU Horizon 2020 project FRAMEwork** explores the potential to replicate the Farmer Cluster model across Europe to enhance farmland biodiversity at a continental scale. Between 2020 and 2021, eleven clusters, regrouping 124 farms, were established in eight countries: the UK, Austria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Spain, and varied in size, farming system, organisational structure, and the degree of connectivity between farms. Biodiversity-friendly practices introduced by the Farmer Clusters include the introduction of wildflower margins, meadow restoration, hedgerow and tree planting, and the installation of bat and bird boxes. Leaning on experiences from the FRAMEwork project, this policy brief explains how Farmer Clusters can play a role in promoting biodiversity, ecosystem services and sustainable farming practices; collaboration and knowledge exchange; and landscape-scale biodiversity monitoring.

Evidence of impact

By fostering collaboration among farmers within shared landscapes, Farmer Clusters serve as platforms for implementing sustainable practices, spurring innovation, and enhancing ecological resilience.

- **Identity change drives lasting behaviour**

Facilitated Farmer Clusters allow farmers to reimagine their role in biodiversity conservation. Through trust and peer exchange, they realise the transition from isolated efforts to collaborative, nature-friendly practices. This shift in identity—from compliance to stewardship—encourages long-term behavioural change. Interviews show that many farmers embraced terms like “nature-friendly farming” and developed a deeper sense of responsibility, turning sceptics into advocates and embedding conservation values in rural communities (Bohnet et al., 2025).

- **Tangible ecosystem benefits and sustainable practices**

Farmer Clusters can deliver real environmental gains—from improved soil health to increased biodiversity. Localised practices, such as zero tillage and cover cropping in Scotland’s Buchan cluster, enhance soil life and retention. In Austria flower strips and species-rich grasslands restore pollinator habitats and floral diversity. In the Netherlands, France and Italy, clusters focused on improving natural pest control and sustainable farming, illustrating how collective action benefits both nature and agriculture.

- **Landscape-scale biodiversity monitoring and citizen science**

Monitoring is vital for understanding the effectiveness of conservation measures and guiding result-based payments. FRAMEwork adapted and tested protocols used in existing monitoring schemes for use within Farmer Clusters, allowing farmers to assess changes in habitats and species across farms. In addition, involving communities in data collection through citizen science methods creates a shared understanding of ecological changes across the landscape, build trust between farmers and the public, and foster a sense of shared purpose. They help farmers and communities alike to take ownership of the evidence base that guides

biodiversity conservation, making it more relevant, resilient, and deeply rooted within rural areas.

Policy implications

Successful Farmer Clusters depend on three interlinked pillars: skilled facilitation, access to tailored knowledge and guidance, and well-designed incentives for collaboration. Evidence from the FRAMEwork project across Europe highlights how these elements can work together to drive long-term conservation outcomes.

- **Skilled facilitation is essential**

Facilitators are the linchpins of effective Farmer Clusters. They coordinate meetings, deliver training, monitor progress, and connect farmers with NGOs, researchers, and policymakers. Where facilitation was strong, trust and peer learning flourished; where it was weak, engagement declined. Well-resourced facilitators are vital for building cohesion, sustaining motivation, and ensuring lasting impact (Bohnet et al., 2025). Policy must prioritise **investment in facilitator training and support** to maintain momentum and avoid fragmentation.

- **Access to knowledge, advice, and practical tools**

Farmers need more than goodwill—they need the right information at the right time. Platforms like [Recodo.io](https://recodo.io) provide open-access training, biodiversity monitoring protocols, and stakeholder engagement resources that empower both facilitators and farmers. These tools guide the adoption of effective biodiversity-friendly practices and align local actions with broader conservation goals. Policy should ensure that such platforms are widely accessible, regularly updated, and tailored to local contexts.

- **Incentives that support voluntary, collective action**

Incentives are most effective when they respect farmers’ autonomy and foster collaboration. FRAMEwork findings show that schemes with voluntary collaboration consistently outperform mandatory Farmer Cluster participation. Clusters saw **higher engagement** when incentives allowed **flexible participation** and supported peer-led initiatives. Collective result-based payments enhanced conservation outcomes and **built peer accountability**. Particularly in high-risk settings, collective payments improved cooperation by leveraging the potential for collective risk-sharing. Policymakers should design incentive structures that are adaptable, locally relevant, and rooted in shared goals.

References / Further Reading

Bohnet, I., Thomas, F., Zagata, L., Hardy, C., Fritschle, M., Engel, S., & Kuhfuss, L. (2025). D6.1 Report on the impact of Cluster approach on Farmer's self-identity and behaviour (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15090426>).

To learn more about the FRAMEwork eleven Farmer Cluster, see <https://recodo.io/page/farmer-clusters/farmer-cluster-finder>.

About this Policy Brief

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